

Yasynska Elvira Tsezarivna

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Social Medicine and Public Health, Bukovinian State Medical University, 58002. str. Teatralna 2, Chernivtsi, phone: 380956748935, e-mail:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3768-7278>

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ANALYSIS OF CURRENT HEALTH CARE PROBLEMS IN UKRAINE

Abstract.

The article analyzes the processes of building a stable model of modern health reform implementation in Ukraine and implementation of the "Millennium Development Goals" program. The work focuses on the creation of socially protected and politically stable models of society, which occupy an important place in the implementation of reforms in the field of health care and represent the basis for preserving the human resources of the state. The author highlights the main obstacles to improving the efficiency of health care. In the course of the study, 250 respondents living in the city of Chernivtsi (including internally displaced persons) were interviewed and their answers regarding the main problems of the Ukrainian health care system in difficult situations were analyzed. Conclusions were made regarding the reasons for the increase in the cost of medical services due to the improvement of the qualifications of doctors and the introduction of innovative technologies in the medical field.

Keywords: *quality of medical care, health care management, health care institutions, health care reform, management system, transformation*

Introduction. Currently, in Ukraine, the implementation of reforms in the field of health care is a key component of building a socially protected and politically stable society, ensuring the preservation of the state's human resources. It is important to note that since the beginning of the full-scale war in Ukraine, many medical facilities have been attacked by Russian troops, from which some facilities cannot be restored. The imperfection of the existing mechanisms for regulating the quality of medical care in Ukraine, the lack of a scientifically based domestic quality management system in health care, and insufficient approaches to its development, implementation, and support of interaction with service users at different levels of management emphasize the need to study the role of stakeholders in the quality management of health care institutions health [2].

The priority task of state policy at the moment is the formation of a modern and effective model of the health care system that would meet the challenges of the time, such as COVID-19 and full-scale war. Unfortunately, the existing national health care system does not meet the urgent requirements.

In 2015, the General Assembly summarized the implementation of the "Millennium Development Goals" program and adopted an ambitious resolution, approving a new action plan - "Transforming our world: Agenda for sustainable development until 2030"[6].

This document emphasized the need for world leaders to join forces to implement the plan to "Transform Our World" in a new strategic agenda. The program emphasized that the assigned tasks must be performed with maximum benefit for the present and future generations in accordance with the principles of international law. There was a desire to carry out the tasks in such a way that they bring maximum benefit to both current and future generations, observing the principles of compliance with international law. The main ones are: universal eradication of poverty and hunger,

achievement of food security, promotion of sustainable development of agriculture; ensuring a healthy lifestyle; provision of inclusive and quality education; ensuring gender equality; promotion of continuous, sustainable economic growth; reducing inequality within and between countries; implementation of urgent measures to combat climate change and its consequences; strengthening, implementation and activation of global partnership and cooperation for sustainable development, etc. [6].

Accordingly, budget expenditures and the amount of used resources are increasing due to a number of factors:

- increase in population aging rates;
- decrease of people who follow a healthy lifestyle;
- appearance of new diseases;
- destabilization of the mental state of citizens (consequences of Russian aggression), etc.

The level of public health and the health care system is a complex factor affecting national economic security. National security covers the entire spectrum of social development, including health care. In addition, due to the improvement of the qualification level of doctors and the introduction of innovative technologies in the medical field, there is a tendency to increase the cost of medical services, which, in turn, leads to an increase in citizens' demands for the quality of these services [7].

Presenting main material.

The purpose of the article: Analysis and generalization of the problems of reforming the health care system based on respondents' answers regarding the modern Ukrainian health care system in difficult situations.

Materials and methods: We were interviewed 250 respondents living in the city of Chernivtsi (including 60 internally displaced persons). The sociological survey was based on a questionnaire specially created by us, which consisted of questions about the main

shortcomings of modern health care and assessment of one's own health.

The level of health largely depends on the quality of medical services, and investments in health ensure the stable existence of its economic levers. Decreasing the level of health, morbidity and disability lead to loss of working capacity. Health, as an important characteristic of human capital, labor potential and the quality of the workforce, is not taken into account by economists in full. Unfortunately, the fact that the deterioration of the health of employees is directly related to the quality of their work is often underestimated.

In our opinion, there are main obstacles to improving the efficiency of health care:

- insufficient statistical and analytical base for making effective management decisions and many controversial issues in regulatory and legal acts;
- business entities are limited in their free choice regarding political, economic and organizational freedoms that provide medical services;
- the existence of bureaucratic obstacles regarding the approval of the legal framework;
- departure of many doctors abroad in connection with Russian aggression, reduction of experienced and qualified specialists;
- reluctance of medical staff to implement new changes;
- insufficient financial support of the health care sector and the imperfection of the network of health care institutions.

We were interviewed 250 respondents living in the city of Chernivtsi (including internally displaced persons). 240 respondents (96%) consider corruption to be the main problem in health care; 190 respondents noted the high cost of medicines (79%). The respondents also noted the following: ensuring the doctor's responsibility for the patient's health and the obtained results of treatment - 154 (61.6%); setting adequate prices for pharmacy drugs and providing medical services in medical institutions 148 (59.2%); provision of military personnel with discounted medicines in full and high-quality medical services with state funds 146 (58.4%).

In addition, some respondents paid attention to the availability of "voluntary funds" in hospitals, especially in maternity hospitals 138 (55.2%); the need to increase control over the quality control of the work of medical workers 125 (50%); salary increase for doctors and average medical personnel 118 (47.2%).

According to the results of the sociological survey, it was found that 180 (72%) respondents did not feel any changes in their health after the full-scale Russian invasion, 70 (28%) noted a deterioration in their health (appearance of psycho-emotional disorders and cardiovascular diseases). Among the respondents of internally displaced persons, 34 persons (56.7%) out of 60 experienced significant neuropsychological deterioration, and 10 persons (16.7%) aged 45 years and older emphasized the appearance of cardiovascular diseases against the background of psycho-emotional stress.

Today, it is easiest to assess the level of quality of the health care system using a survey of the population regarding satisfaction with the services received. The

patient's satisfaction with the interaction with the medical subsystem is defined by the WHO European Bureau as one of the elements that must be paid attention to in order to ensure the quality of medical care [7].

It is clear that at the present moment, new theoretically formed comprehensive changes to the health care model are needed, which are related to the freedom of choice of citizens and have a positive effect on improving the quality of medical services. Taking into account the limit of budget funds allocated for health care, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at rationalizing the demand for receiving medical services, but as a result, it is possible to increase the waiting period of citizens for certain types of treatment.

So, quality management in a health care facility covers three main areas:

- Creating the quality of medical care.
 - Quality control and improvement.
 - Improvement of the modern health care system.
 - Development of standards, monitoring, audit, change management system in healthcare.
- The training of healthcare management specialists should begin with the development of management models based on the following principles and requirements:
- Multilevel impact of management actions.
 - The multidimensional nature of the regulatory work of managers.
 - Non-linearity of modern approaches to the organization of management processes.
 - The choice of alternative options for the development of the management system.
 - Identification of medical organizations taking into account their structure and specifics of activity.
 - Integration of the management model with organizational, informational and innovative, technological and economic components.
 - Balanced management actions.
 - Adjustment of the management system based on detected deviations in the activities of medical institutions.
 - The stability of the development of the health care system at all levels of its functioning.

It is worth emphasizing that the effectiveness of management models in Ukraine does not achieve the expected results due to the economic damage associated with Russian aggression, organizational and methodical difficulties. Undoubtedly, this has a negative effect on the positive dynamics of increasing the efficiency of health care. It is possible to change the concept of systemic transformation of health care management only by modernizing the models of medical institutions. It is necessary to conduct a constant analysis of the emergence of new unforeseen situations and adaptation of economic and socio-psychological conditions.

The effectiveness of the health care system depends on the quality of training of managers in this area and their ability to respond accordingly to structural changes in the management of health care facilities. The modern practice of managing medical facilities during reforms has proven the existence of flexibility, relevance and orientation to the received. However, the

problem of relations with interested parties (stakeholders) remains relevant. The main task of interaction with stakeholders from the standpoint of quality is to create conditions that will ensure the successful and stable development of the health care facility, while minimizing strategic risks and surprises.

Conclusion.

Today, it is easiest to assess the level of quality of the health care system with the help of a population survey on satisfaction with the services received. Creation of the optimal functioning of the management system of medical institutions of Ukraine in the conditions of development of a balanced management system will allow in the future to create the influence of external and internal factors should take into account the appropriate conditions for the formation of the medical services market.

References:

1. Gajdenko, OV & Koshky`n, KV Stejxoldery` medy`chny`x proektiv [Stakeholders of medical projects]. /Upravlinnya proektamy` ta rozvy`tok vy`robny`cztva. 2016, no. 2(58), pp. 12-18.
2. Gorachuk VV (2015) Medyko-sotsial'ne obhruntuvannya modeli systemy upravlinnya yakistyu medychnoyi dopomohy [Medico-social substantiation of the model of quality management system of medical care] Kyiv, NAPE named after PL Shupik, 440 p.
3. Kotliar A. "Viina ta skhemy v medytsyni". <https://zn.ua/SOCIUM/vojna-i-skhemy-v-meditsine.html>.
4. Slabkiy GO, Parhomenko GY, Astahova NY. Health 2020 - New European Policy and Strategy In the Interest of Health Population. Bulletin of problems in biology and medicine. 2014; Issue 3 (110): 16-20. <https://vpbm.com.ua/ua/vpbm-2014-03-1/6408> [in Ukrainian].
5. Schwab K. (2017). Global Competitiveness Index 2017-2018 Rankings. URL: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/GCR20172018/05_Full_Report/The_Global_Competitiveness_Report_2017%E2%80%932018.pdf.
6. Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. United Nations. 2015: 41 p. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld/publication>.
7. WHO European regional office (2019) Health in Europe Report 2018: More than just numbers: facts for all [Electronic resource]. Available at <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/330083/9789289054515-rus.pdf>.